

Report to National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Ocean Exploration on status and use of biological material collected via NOAA Ship *Okeanos Explorer*

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I. Highlights Among 2025 Activities

- 214 Items cataloged, 139 specimen lots, 67 genetic samples, and 8 image-only lots
- 265 eDNA samples accessioned into collection
- 382 Metabarcoding libraries provided to AOML colleagues incorporated into NCBI and the Ocean DNA Explorer
- 1,082 DNA extractions from specimens
- 1,190 new genome skimming datasets produced
- 1 new species described

II. Background

Staff from the National Systematics Laboratory (NSL) of NOAA National Marine Fisheries Service and the Department of Invertebrate Zoology of Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History (NMNH-IZ) work to extend the exploration activities carried out by NOAA Ocean Exploration (OE) via NOAA Ship *Okeanos Explorer* by incorporating collected biological material, both specimens and environmental samples, into the US National Collections. This work ensures the preservation and long-term maintenance of collected biological material so that they can be studied to build biological knowledge subsequent to cruise activities, amplifying their impact. Personnel that have worked on *Okeanos* biological material since the vessel was equipped to make collections in 2015:

Abigail Reft –	Museum Specialist of NSL
Allen Collins –	Curator, Director of NSL
Bill Moser –	Collection Manager of NMNH-IZ
Katie Ahlfeld –	Museum Specialist of NMNH-IZ
Courtney Wickel –	Museum Technician (no longer with NMNH-IZ)
Stephanie Bush –	Support Scientist (genetic work) of NMNH-IZ
Steven Auscavitch –	Support Scientist (genetic work) of NMNH-IZ

All personnel have a background in biology and/or museum collection management. Collection management activities included transaction management (acquisitions, loans and returns), curation, cataloging, and data entry using the NMNH cataloging software, EMu (Axiell Group Electronic Museum). Prior to the hire of Abigail Reft, these duties were carried out by Katie Ahlfeld and Courtney Wickel. As of January 2018, all curation and data duties have been performed by Abigail Reft. Stephanie Bush, Steven Auscavitch and Allen Collins have participated in subsampling and/or genetic characterization of organismal specimens,

and Steven Auscavitch, Allen Collins and NOAA-OE and NMNH supported interns have worked on environmental samples to extract eDNA and conduct metabarcoding.

As specimen lots (Tables 1,2) and eDNA derived from water samples (Table 3) are cataloged, identification and station data associated with collection events are stored directly on the museum’s file server. This server-based, multimedia cataloging application provides robust data entry, edit, query, reporting, and WWW-public access capabilities. The NMNH-IZ catalog is accessible to the public through links from the Museum’s web site (<http://naturalhistory.si.edu/>) or directly at <http://collections.nmnh.si.edu/search/iz/>. The web-based catalog offers the user comprehensive search tools and the ability to download search results to a *.csv file for import into other database or spreadsheet software or a *.kml file for use in GIS and mapping applications. All specimens associated with NOAA can be quickly searched at the NMNH website (<https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/search/iz/>) using the “Search by Field” option and querying for “NOAA collections” in the “Collection Name.” All specimens and samples specifically collected via NOAA Ship *Okeanos Explorer* can be searched by selecting “NOAA National Ocean Exploration & Research (OER) Collection” in the “Collection Name” field or by selecting “Okeanos Explorer R/V” in the list of vessels. When the new NOAA ship *Discoverer* is commissioned, samples and specimens collected on its expeditions will be similarly searchable.

III. Loans and cataloged material

After cataloging (Tables 1-3), material has been loaned out for morphological and genetic work to multiple institutions both in the US and internationally (Tables 4-7). Some of these loans are for the genetic subsample rather than the whole specimen. Total amount of material deposited in the NMNH collection, broken down by cruise, as of February 2026, is summarized in Tables 1, 2, and 3 for invertebrates, fishes, and eDNA, respectively.

Table 1. Invertebrate specimens cataloged.

Cruise #	Acquire #	Total number of cataloged specimen lots	Unique Genetic Biorepository samples (eDNA)	Total Biorepository samples
EX1502	2088044	3 videos, no specimens		
EX1504	2074385	109 (7 unique and total genetic samples)	7	7
EX1603, 1605, 1606	2078414	184 (includes 2 HURL samples)	4	6
EX1702, 1703, 1705	2081016	253	1	1
EX1706	2081735	78		
EX1708	2082361	139		
EX1711	2083404	109		
EX1803	2084229	68	20	20
EX1806	2084230	171	95	192
EX1811	2085629	87	40	40
EX1903L2	2087006	150	97	110
EX1905L2	2087570	121	77	79
EX1907	2087951	74	51	54
EX2103	2089676	12	6	6
EX2104	2089676	71	63	69
EX2107	2089977	84	73, 70 eDNA	143

EX2201	2090200/ 2091221 eDNA	3	3, 10 eDNA	13
EX2203	2090999		46 eDNA only	46
EX2205	2091221	153	61, 48 eDNA	112
EX2206	2091221	48	23, 29 eDNA	52
EX2301	2092866	43	43	43
EX2304	2093446	53	30	33 (4 of these samples are of a bacterial mat, cataloged as an environmental sample)
EX2306	2093688	303 (plus 3 image lots)	101	102
EX2502	2096336	5	4	4
EX2503	2096512	131	59	60
Various		6 lots of photographs only (spm not collected)		
	Total Cataloged: 3661	2457 specimen lots, and 3 video and 9 image lots	858, 203 eDNA	1192 total BR (includes eDNA)

Note: the above numbers change slightly as specimen lots, which may contain more than one individual as well as biological associates, get separated into separate lots. Such separation can occur for a variety of reasons – e.g., to separate distinct species, to separate a sample that gets stained and scanned with the microCT, or to separate subsamples such as tissues or DNA extractions that become part of the NMNH cryofacility (Biorepository) – with the goal of tracking data associated with specific material samples.

Table 2. Fish specimens cataloged.

Cruise #	Total number of cataloged lots
EX1702, 1703, 1705	1 (1 unique genetic sample, 2 total)
EX1708	2
EX1803	1
EX1806	5 (5 unique and total genetic samples)
EX1903L2	5 (5 unique genetic samples, 10 total)
EX2304	1 (1 genetic sample)
Total cataloged	15 (and 18 Biorepository samples)

Note: Two lots of unidentified eggs, from EX1903L2 and EX2304, that were previously cataloged in IZ were discovered to be fish eggs and moved to NMNH-VZ-Fishes.

Table 3. Summary of eDNA derived from water samples.

Cruise #	Total number of lots (includes Field Blank samples)	Number extracted	Number cataloged
EX2107	70, all extracted and cataloged	70	70
EX2201	10, all extracted and cataloged	10	10
EX2203	46, all extracted and cataloged	46	46
EX2205	60, all extracted and cataloged	60	60
EX2206	33, all extracted	33	29
EX2301	76	76	
EX2303	12	12	

EX2304	35 water samples plus 4 samples from bacterial mat	12	4
EX2306	69	0	
EX2403	24	0	
EX2502	33		
EX2503	62		
EX2505	8		
EX2506	70		
EX2507	92		
Total	700 water samples and 4 bacterial mat eDNA samples	319	219

Table 4. Loan activity (2015-Dec 2025)

Cruise #	Acquire #	# lots loaned total
EX1504	2074385	47
EX1603, 1605, 1606	2078414	61
EX1702, 1703, 1705	2081016	62
EX1706	2081735	20
EX1708	2082361	43
EX1711	2083404	22
EX1803	2084229	17
EX1806	2084230	38
EX1811	2085629	43
EX1903L2	2087006	31
EX1905L2	2087570	24
EX1907	2087951	30
EX2103	2089676	2
EX2104	2089676	22
EX2107	2089977	29
EX2205, 2206	2091221	39
EX2301	2092866	1
EX2304	2093446	7
EX2306	2093688	18
EX2503	2096512	3
Total		559 total lots loaned 73 total loan requests

Table 5. Loan activity by taxon.

Taxon	# lots loaned total
Cnidaria: Octocorals	199
All other Cnidarians	67
Poriferans	187
Arthropods	50
Annelida: Polychaetes	6

Echinoderms	39
Molluscs	10

Loans of Okeanos material have been granted to various researchers at different institutions (Table 6). The list below does not include interal activity at NMNH. Known staff and visitors/students/fellows that have significantly studied Okeanos material are listed in the subsequent table (Table 7). This is an underestimate of the visitors that have accessed the material on visits to the museum as we do not track every lot that visitors/students/fellows study. Some researchers appear in both Tables 6 and 7 because they have studied the material at the Smithsonian and subsequently requested a loan of some of the Okeanos material.

Table 6. Scientists from outside institutions who have officially requested loans.

Country	Institution	Researcher	Student(if applicable)
United States	American Museum of Natural History	Estefania Rodriguez	Mercer R. Brugler
United States	Bernice P. Bishop Museum	Holly Bolick	
United States	California Academy of Science	Richard Mooi	
United States	California Academy of Science	Terry Gosliner	Kelly Markello
United States	California State University Fullerton	Doug Eernisse	Doug Eernisse
Australia	CSIRO Oceans and Atmosphere	Alan Williams	Candice Untiedt
United States	Field Museum of Natural History	Rudiger Bieler	Tauana Cunha
Canada	Fisheries and Oceans Canada	Lindsay Beazley	
United States	Florida International University-Biscayne Bay Campus	Heather Bracken-Grissom	
United States	Harvard University (MCZ)	Gonzalo Giribet	Paula Rodríguez-Flores
United States	Harvey Mudd College	Catherine McFadden	Catherine McFadden
United States	Lehigh University	Santiago Herrera	Elizabeth Whitson
Germany	Max Planck Institute for Chemistry	Alfredo Martinez-Garcia	Tanja Wald
Brazil	Museu Nacional	Eduardo Hajdu	Cristiana Castello-Branco
France	Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle	Aude Andouche	
France	Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle	Pierre Lozouet	Tina N. Molodtsova
Australia	Museum Victoria	Timothy O'Hara	
United States	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - National Ocean Service	Peter Etnoyer	Janessy Frometa
Singapore	National University of Singapore	Swee Cheng Lim	
United Kingdom	Natural History Museum	Lucy Woodall	Michelle Taylor
United Kingdom	Natural History Museum	Adrian Glover	Magdalena Georgieva
United States	NOAA NWFS	Krista Nichols	Meredith Everett

United States	Northeastern University, Marine Science Center	Daniel Distel	Ann Evankow
United States	NOVA Southeastern University	Charles Messing	
United States	NOVA Southeastern University	Timothy Swain	
Australia	Queensland Museum	Paul Muir	Jeremy Horowitz
Australia	Queensland Museum	Paul Muir	Jeremy Horowitz
Israel	Tel Aviv University	Yehuda Benayahu	
United States	Texas A&M University	Mary Wicksten	
United Kingdom	The Natural History Museum of London	Ana Riesgo	
Colombia	Universidad de Los Andes	Adriana Rodriguez	Adriana Rodriguez
Spain	Universidad de Sevilla	Pablo López-González	
Portugal	Universidade dos Acores	Marina Carreiro-Silva	
Portugal	Universidade dos Acores	Marina Carreiro-Silva	Teresa Cerqueira, Manuela Ramos
Brazil	Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro	Eduardo Hajdu	Cristiana Castello-Branco
Brazil	Universidade Federal Rural de Pernambuco	Ralf Cordeiro	
France	Universite de La Rochelle	Eric Pante	
Norway	University of Bergen	Hans Tore Rapp	Jon Thomassen Hestetun
United States	University of California, Los Angeles	Aradhna Tripati	Aradhna Tripati
United States	University of California, San Diego (SCRIPPS)	Greg W. Rouse	
United States	University of California, San Diego, (SCRIPPS),	Greg Rouse	Dong Dong
Denmark	University of Copenhagen	Anders Garm	
United Kingdom	University of Essex	Michelle Taylor	
United States	University of Florida	Gustav Paulay	Tania Pineda
Sweden	University of Gothenburg	Rhian Waller	Lara Beckmann
United States	University of Louisiana at Lafayette	Scott France	Jaymes Awbrey
United States	University of Louisiana at Lafayette	Scott France	Katie Musser
United States	University of Louisiana at Lafayette	Scott France	Upasana Ganguly
United States	University of Louisiana at Lafayette	Scott France	Jaymes Awbrey
United States	University of Texas Rio Grande Valley	David Hicks	Erin Easton
Japan	University of the Ryukyus	James Reimer	Maria Eduarda Alves dos Santos
Canada	Canadian Museum of Nature	Jean-Marc Gagnon	
United States	Southern Utah University	Bonnie Bain	

France	Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle	Laure Corbari	Paula Rodriguez-Flores
Japan	University of the Ryukyus	James Reimer	Chloe Fourreau
United States	George Washington University	Marcos Perez-Losada	Meng-Chen Yu

Table 7. Resident staff and visitors who have worked on Okeanos material at NMNH.

Name	Home Institution	Position
Allen Collins	NOAA/NMNH	Curator
Chris Mah	NMNH	Research Associate
Stephen Cairns	NMNH	Emeritus curator
Rafael Lemaitre	NMNH	Emeritus curator
Jerry Harasewych	NMNH	Emeritus curator
Karen Osborn	NMNH	Curator
Hyacinth Suarez	Holy Name University (Philippines)	Visitor
Jin-Ho Park	George Washington University	Visitor, later Postdoctoral fellow
Nick Bezio	University of Maryland/NMN	PhD Student
Brett Gonzalez	NMNH	Postdoctoral fellow
Michael Ford	NOAA	Research Associate
Dennis Opresko	NMNH	Research Associate
Carmen Cobo	NMNH	MDBC postdoctoral fellow
Camille Leal	NMNH	MDBC postdoctoral fellow
Declan Morrissey	NMNH	MDBC postdoctoral fellow
Paula Rodriguez Flores	NMNH	MDBC postdoctoral fellow
Claudia Vaga	NMNH	MDBC postdoctoral fellow
Jeremy Horowitz	NMNH	MDBC postdoctoral fellow
Steven Auscavitch	NMNH	Trust Employee
Adena Collens	University of Maryland/NMNH	PhD student
Chloe Fourreau	University of Ryukyus	Visitor
Harold Carlson	University of Hawaii	Visitor
Meng-chen Yu	George Washington University	Postdoctoral fellow
Arthur Anker	unaffiliated	Visitor
Amanda Windsor	FDA	Visitor
Antonio C. Marques	University of Sao Paulo	Visitor
Bonnie Bain	Southern Utah University	Visitor
Chloe Fourreau	University of the Ryukyus	Visitor
Meng-Chen Yu	George Washington University	Visitor

IV. Genetic Characterization of Okeanos Specimens

Since 2023, our team has worked to derive genetic sequences from Okeanos specimens (progress summarized in Table 8). These genetic sequences are valuable for a number of reasons. First, they serve to build genetic reference libraries for deep sea marine life, a necessary resource for informing eDNA metabarcoding and metagenomic based analyses of deep-sea biological communities. These genetic sequences also provide essential information for taxonomy, species delimitation, and phylogenetic systematics analyses.

Initial genetic work carried out at NMNH focused on barcoding a fragment of the mitochondrial COX1 gene and depositing the resulting sequences in the Barcode of Life Database (BOLD). More recent efforts focus on genome skimming, a method by which next generation sequencing techniques are used to generate limited amounts of whole genome sequencing, from which high copy regions in the genome can be assembled. Such regions include the entire mitochondrial genome and ribosomal repeat regions. COX1 barcoding continues, but genome skimming has become the focus of genetic efforts going forward as it provides higher success rates, significantly greater amounts of data at limited extra cost, and large amounts of ancillary data representing the genomes of the targeted specimens, as well as those from biological associates.

The first several Okeanos cruises (2015-2017) that collected material sent genetic samples to the Ocean Genome Legacy (OGL). In 2024, several vouchers from these earlier cruises were subsampled again at the museum to genome skim and generate accessible genetic samples from the remnant DNA extractions as OGL is not easy or affordable for many researchers to access. Any remaining DNA extract will be deposited in the NMNH biorepository for future use and will eventually be included in the genetic samples in table 1. In table 9 below, we have tabulated samples from some of the earliest cruises that we have subsequently subsampled and genome skimmed. We have established [NCBI BioProject PRJNA1072111](#) to track BioSamples (specimens), raw sequence read archives (SRA; genome skims), and derived Nucleotide data (assembled sequences).

During 2025 we have started to opportunistically integrate specimens from other NOAA Ocean Exploration and Ocean Exploration Cooperative Institute-supported expeditions (e.g. Ocean Exploration Trust E/V *Nautilus*) into reference library development. The Museum of Comparative Zoology, primary repository for the Ocean Exploration Trust, has cataloged >4500 deep-sea invertebrate and fish specimens that represent a largely untapped reservoir of voucher-based genetic references. Efforts to incorporate these specimens into eDNA reference libraries began at scale in FY22-23 via a NOAA OE NOFO award to Steve Auscavitch (Boston University) and Meredith Everett (NOAA-NWFSC) to sequence deep-sea corals throughout the US Pacific Remote Islands from specimens collected in 2018-2023. During this time, 277 deep-sea octocorals were sequenced from across the central Pacific. At NMNH in 2025, we sequenced an additional 298 specimens with genome skimming from E/V *Nautilus* collections including deep-sea corals, sponges, and other invertebrate taxa (Table 10). These efforts will continue in parallel with Okeanos Explorer collections sequencing through calendar year 2026 as resources permit.

Table 8. Summary of progress in genetically sequencing biological specimens.

Cruise #	Total unique NMNH samples	Tissues sampled	Genome skimmed
EX1504	109	80	70
EX1603	20	16	16
EX1605	118	95	90
EX1606	42	37	34
EX1702	95	42	42
EX1703	92	40	40
EX1705	71	30	30

EX1706	76	5	5
EX1708	139	2	2
EX1711	108	0	0
EX1803	88	0	0
EX1806	93	95	3
EX1811	40	40	54
EX1903L2	97	97	13
EX1905L2	77	79	18
EX1907	49	52	17
EX2103	6	6	7
EX2104	63	69	58
EX2107	73	45	13
EX2201	3	3	3
EX2205	65	65	59
EX2206	48	41	0
EX2301	43	36	36
EX2304	30	34	34
EX2306	101	102	102
Total	1877	1262	901

Note: In some cases, there are more tissues sampled than unique NMNH tissues. This is because sometimes more than one tissue is sampled per NMNH lot or the morphological voucher was directly sampled for tissue. Additionally, specimens out on loan might not be accessible for reference library work until they are returned to the collection.

Table 9. Summary of progress on resampling effort

Cruise #	Specimen lots sampled for genetic work
EX1504	84
EX1603	19
EX1605	77
EX1606	34

Table 10. Additional specimen sequencing conducted in 2025 to supplement DNA reference library efforts with specimens collected by NOAA Ocean Exploration-supported expeditions on E/V *Nautilus*.

E/V <i>Nautilus</i> cruise	Genome skims produced
NA017	1
NA052	53
NA085	1
NA149	39
NA153	32
NA167	3
NA174	136

Other	33
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V. Genetic Characterization of eDNA Samples

From environmental samples of water, 319 samples have been extracted into eDNA samples (Table 3). From 291 eDNA samples, metabarcoding libraries for COX1, 18S_v4, and 12S have been generated and shared with NOAA AOML, who are leading a data release paper. Additional marker regions (28S and 18S_v9) have been generated for a subset of samples for EX2301. During 2025, our team delivered all eDNA metabarcoding data thus far generated to colleagues (Luke Thompson’s group) at NOAA AOML, along with all protocols in Better Biomolecular Ocean Practices (BeBOP) standards and collection metadata that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). Through this effort, all raw sequence data have been deposited in [NCBI under BioProject PRJNA1284389](#). During 2026, eDNA observations to explore deep-sea communities sampled by NOAA Ship *Okeanos Explorer* will become available via AOML’s [Ocean DNA Explorer website](#) and the [Ocean Biodiversity Information System \(OBIS\)](#) through AOML’s integrated bioinformatics platform for data processing, visualization, curation, and publication.

VI. Additional Okeanos Explorer Collection Activities during 2025

The NOAA-NMNH collaboration focused on Mesophotic and Deep Benthic Communities (MDBC) impacted by the Deep Water Horizon Oil Spill continued in 2025. Five MDBC postdocs worked on Okeanos material collected from the Gulf. In addition, Allen Collins, Steve Auscavitch, and Abigail Reft made a concerted effort to characterize the golden orb sample (USNM 1699903, EX2306y_D07_04B), both genetically and morphologically, collected in 2023 to understand this sample. This work resulted in resolution to the enigmatic nature of this specimen, and a manuscript draft was initiated.

We had two longer-term visitors that made use of the Okeanos collections to look for associations. Chloe Fourreau studied corals looking for associated polychaetes and Harold Carlson studied both sponges and corals for eggs of invertebrates and fishes. Furthermore, local postdoctoral fellow Meng-chen Yu has helped update several barnacle identifications and will continue to work on barnacle samples.

During the year, we cataloged some images taken during Okeanos cruises of uncollected sea stars in aid of Chris Mah’s continued research. Allen Collins and Abigail Reft have attended meetings to help streamline the labels generated for the samples in the field and other data concerns. Allen Collins gave a summary of progress genetically characterizing Okeanos specimens for biannual meeting of the Interagency Working Group for Ocean Exploration and Characterization (IWG-OEC) during the late fall of 2025. In December 2025, Steve Auscavitch gave a talk with MDBC postdoc Paula Rodríguez Flores in the Crustal Ocean Biosphere Research Accelerator (COBRA) [webinar series](#) on “Harmonizing eDNA reference library development and taxonomy to close knowledge gaps in deep-sea biodiversity”. The talk highlighted work on reference library development using NOAA Ocean Exploration-supported cruise specimens from the *Okeanos Explorer* and E/V *Nautilus* and ongoing eDNA sequencing. The webinar received 145 registrants per COBRA statistics.

As a result of resampling some of the earliest collected Okeanos specimens mentioned above, some subsamples mistakenly cataloged separately under their own number were found and cleaned up. A few extra associates were identified and cataloged separately from their host specimen.

VII. Publications and new species through 2025

- Anker, A. On a remarkable new stenopodid shrimp (Decapoda: Stenopodidea) from the bathyal depths of the tropical western Atlantic. *Zootaxa*. 5701 (1): 079-090.
- Bezio, N., Collins, A. G. 2024. Redescription of the deep-sea benthic ctenophore genus *Tjalfiella* from the North Atlantic (Class Tentaculata, Order Platyctenida, Family Tjalfiellidae). *Zootaxa*. 5486 (2): 241–266.
- Bledsoe-Becerra, Y.M., Whittaker, I.S., Horowitz, J., Naranjo, K.M., Johnson-Rosemond, J., Mullins, K.H., Cunningham, K.M., Shetty, S., Messinides, S.N., Behney, M.S. and Fehsal, J.A., 2022. Mitogenomics reveals low variation within a trigenic complex of black corals from the North Pacific Ocean. *Organisms Diversity & Evolution*. 22 (2): 343-353.
- Cairns, S. D. 2017. New Species of Stylasterid (Cnidaria: Hydrozoa: Anthoathecata: Stylasteridae) from the Northwestern Hawaiian Islands. *Pac. Sci.* 71 (1): 77-81.
- Cairns, S. D. 2018. Primnoidae (Cnidaria: Octocorallia: Calcaxonia) of the Okeanos Explorer expeditions (CAPSTONE) to the central Pacific. *Zootaxa*. 4532 (1): 001-043.
- Cairns, S.D., 2021. A new species of azooxanthellate Scleractinia from the western Atlantic, and a new name and record of *Desmophyllum striatum* sensu Cairns, 1979. *Proceedings of the Biological Society of Washington*. 134(1): 1-5.
- Castello-Branco, C., Collins A. G., Hajdu E. 2020. A collection of hexactinellids (Porifera) from the deep South Atlantic and North Pacific: new genus, new species and new records. *PeerJ*. DOI 10.7717/peerj.9431: 1-28.
- Cordeiro, R.T., Cairns, S.D. and Perez, C.D., 2017. A revision of the genus *Radicipes* stearns, 1883 (Anthozoa: Octocorallia: Chrysogorgiidae). *Zootaxa*, 4319 (1): 1-26.
- Farfan, G.A., McKeown, D.A. and Post, J.E., 2023. Mineralogical characterization of biosilicas versus geological analogs. *Geobiology*. 21(4): 520-533.
- Ford, M., Bezio N., Collins A. 2020. *Duobrachium sparksae* (incertae sedis Ctenophora Tentaculata Cydippida): A new genus and species of benthopelagic ctenophore seen at 3,910 m depth off the coast of Puerto Rico. *Plankton Benthos Res.* 15 (4): 296-305.
- Ganguly, U., France, S. C. 2024. Expanded distribution and a new genus for rock-inhabiting sea pens (Cnidaria, Anthozoa, Octocorallia, Pennatuloidae). *Zootaxa*. 5507 (1): 123-139.
- Hestetun, J. T., Rapp, H. T., Pomponi, S. 2019. Deep-Sea Carnivorous Sponges from the Mariana Islands. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 6 (371): 1-22.
- Horowitz, J., Barajas, M., McCartin, L. J., Vohsen, S. A., Herrera, S. 2025. Description of a new species of *Stauropathes* (Anthozoa, Antipatharia, Schizopathidae) from Puerto Rico. *ZooKeys*. 1231: 331-346.
- Kise, H., Montenegro, J., Santos, M.E., Hoeksema, B.W., Ekins, M., Ise, Y., Higashiji, T., Fernandez-Silva, I. and Reimer, J.D., 2022. Evolution and phylogeny of glass-sponge-associated zoantharians, with

- a description of two new genera and three new species. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*. 194 (1): 323-347.
- López-González, P.J., 2021. *Scytalium herklotsi* sp. nov. (Anthozoa, Octocorallia, Pennatulacea), the first Atlantic species in the genus *Scytalium* Herklots, 1858. *Marine Biodiversity*. 51 (4): 62.
- López-González, P.J., 2022. Molecular phylogeny and morphological comparison of the deep-sea genus *Alloptilella* Li, Zhan & Xu, 2021 (Octocorallia, Pennatulacea). *Marine Biodiversity*, 52 (4): 41.
- Mah, C. 2024. Two New Taxa of Goniasteridae (Asteroidea, Echinodermata) and Noteworthy Observations of Deep-Sea Asteroidea by the NOAA Ship Okeanos Explorer in the North and Tropical Atlantic. *Zootaxa*. 5432 (4): 461-508.
- Mah, C. 2020. New species, occurrence records and observations of predation by deep-sea Asteroidea (Echinodermata) from the North Atlantic by NOAA ship Okeanos Explorer. *Zootaxa*. 4766 (2): 201-260.
- Mah, C. 2022. New genera, species and occurrences of deep-sea Asteroidea (Valvatacea, Forcipulatacea, Echinodermata) collected from the North Pacific ocean by the CAPSTONE expedition. *Zootaxa*. 5164 (1): 001-075.
- Molodtsova, T.N., Opresko, D.M. and Wagner, D., 2022. Description of a new and widely distributed species of *Bathypathes* (Cnidaria: Anthozoa: Antipatharia: Schizopathidae) previously misidentified as *Bathypathes alternata* Brook, 1889. *PeerJ*. 10: e12638.
- Molodtsova, T.N., Opresko, D.M., O'Mahoney, M., Simakova, U.V., Kolyuchkina, G.A., Bledsoe, Y.M., Nasiadka, T.W., Ross, R.F. and Brugler, M.R., 2023. One of the deepest genera of Antipatharia: taxonomic position revealed and revised. *Diversity*. 15 (3): 436.
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To date, 44 new species have been described from material collected by the Okeanos Explorer (Table 11).

Table 11. Type designations of Okeanos material.

*indicates that the lot is a video taken by Okeanos (no specimen was collected).

USNM #	New species	Type designation	Authority (publication)
1294083	<i>Crypthelia kelleyi</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2017
1453718	<i>Callogorgia cracentis</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1467625	<i>Calyptrophora carinata</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1424085	<i>Calyptrophora distolos</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1424218	<i>Calyptrophora lyra</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1453726	<i>Calyptrophora pourtalesi</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1467530	<i>Macroprimnoa ornata</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1424215	<i>Narella aurantiaca</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1424208	<i>Narella calamus</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1453829	<i>Narella ferula</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1453764	<i>Narella fordi</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1424202	<i>Narella merga</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1424064	<i>Narella virgosa</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1453670	<i>Paracalyptrophora spiralis</i>	holotype	Cairns, 2018
1424186	<i>Abyssocladia fryerae</i>	holotype	Hestetun et al. 2019
1424180	<i>Abyssocladia kellyae</i>	holotype	Hestetun et al. 2019
1424192	<i>Abyssocladia marianensis</i>	holotype	Hestetun et al. 2019
1424164	<i>Abyssocladia stegosauensis</i>	holotype	Hestetun et al. 2019
1424162	<i>Abyssocladia villosa</i>	holotype	Hestetun et al. 2019
1424095	<i>Chondrocladia (Chondrocladia) coronata</i>	holotype	Hestetun et al. 2019
1424167	<i>Lycopodina subtile</i>	holotype	Hestetun et al. 2019
1424107	<i>Advhena magnifica</i>	holotype	Castello-Branco et al., 2020
1507293	<i>Sibogaster bathyheuretor</i>	holotype	Mah, 2020
1507289	<i>Evoplosoma nizinskiae</i>	holotype	Mah, 2020
1607331*	<i>Duobrachium sparksae</i>	holotype	Ford et al., 2020
1550636	<i>Scytalium herklotsi</i>	holotype	López-González, 2021
1453665	<i>Litonotaster gfoei</i>	holotype	Mah, 2022
1457352	<i>Ceramaster vorax</i>	holotype	Mah, 2022
1457376	<i>Heligmaster kanaloa</i>	holotype	Mah, 2022
1457387	<i>Hippasteria capstonei</i>	holotype	Mah, 2022
1467573	<i>Okeanosaster hohonui</i>	holotype	Mah, 2022
1457372	<i>Evoplosoma nuku</i>	holotype	Mah, 2022
1467554	<i>Bathyceramaster teres</i>	holotype	Mah, 2022
1457371	<i>Bathyceramaster inornata</i>	holotype	Mah, 2022
1467555	<i>Atheraster symphonia</i>	holotype	Mah, 2022
1404092	<i>Umbellapathes litocrada</i>	holotype	Opresko & Wagner, 2020
1404494	<i>Antipathes sylospongia</i>	holotype	Opresko & Wagner, 2020
1404492	<i>Alternatipathes venusta</i>	holotype	Opresko & Wagner, 2020
1660278	<i>Bathyceramaster kelliottae</i>	holotype	Mah, 2024

1658841	<i>Rhianastra isosceles</i>	holotype	Mah, 2024
1550694	<i>Richardina taina</i>	holotype	Anker, 2025

USNM #	New species	Type designation	Authority (publication)
1453657	<i>Calyptrophora distolos</i>	paratype	Cairns, 2018
1467528	<i>Macroprimnoa ornata</i>	paratype	Cairns, 2018
1424086	<i>Macroprimnoa ornata</i>	paratype	Cairns, 2018
1424231	<i>Macroprimnoa ornata</i>	paratype	Cairns, 2018
1467597	<i>Narella aurantiaca</i>	paratype	Cairns, 2018
1457388	<i>Narella calamus</i>	paratype	Cairns, 2018
1467640	<i>Narella virgosa</i>	paratype	Cairns, 2018
1297747	<i>Narella virgosa</i>	paratype	Cairns, 2018
1550630	<i>Evoplosoma nizinskiae</i>	paratype	Mah, 2020
1468988	<i>Umbellapathes litocrada</i>	paratype	Opresko & Wagner, 2020
1467600	<i>Antipathes sylospongia</i>	paratype	Opresko & Wagner, 2020
1607332*	<i>Duobrachium sparksae</i>	paratype	Ford et al., 2020
1607333*	<i>Duobrachium sparksae</i>	paratype	Ford et al., 2020
1424060	<i>Stauropathes monopinnata</i>	paratype	Horowitz et al., 2025
	14 paratypes		

Total # of new species: 44

7 new genera (*Macroprimnoa*, *Advhena*, *Duobrachium*, *Heligmaster*, *Atheraster*, *Okeanosaster*, *Rhianastra*)

VIII. Goals for 2026

- Publish manuscript on the nature of the “Golden Orb”.
- Complete extraction of all remaining eDNA samples (see Table 4).
- Complete cataloging of all uncataloged eDNA samples (see Table 4).
- Publish raw sequence data for all generated eDNA metabarcode profiles via publicly accessible NCBI BioProject.
- Continue to metabarcode eDNA samples (add new markers and complete cox1 and 18S for remaining eDNA samples (see Table 4).
- Give at least two talks presenting progress on genetically characterizing Okeanos specimens.
- Continue to genome skim remaining specimens (Table 9).
- Make genetic data generated from at least 300 Okeanos specimens publicly accessible via NCBI BioProject PRJNA1072111.